

EFFECTIVENESS OF TEACHING STUDENTS IN GROUPS IN THE CLASSROOM

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Abstract. *In the article, the content of organizing the educational process based on the grouping of students in the class and cooperative teaching, among teachers, with the administration, with organizations of students and teachers, leaders, parents, there was talk of establishing cooperative relations among the public. The factors of ensuring high results by dividing the students in the class into groups, using cooperation technology, developing the student's motives for education and implementing the principles of humanization of the educational process are shown.*

Keywords: *division into groups, cooperative teaching, socio-psychological environment, cooperative relations, education, team teaching, teaching in small groups, independent thinking.*

R. Slavin, one of the authors of cooperative learning technology, said that it is not enough to instruct students to complete tasks cooperatively. It is necessary for students to cooperate in the literal sense, to rejoice at the success of each student, to sincerely help each other, and to create a comfortable social and psychological environment. In this technology, when determining the quality of students' knowledge acquisition, they are compared not with each other, but with the previous results of each student. Only then, the students, realizing that the results achieved during the lesson will benefit the team, feel responsible and strive to learn more, acquire knowledge, skills and abilities. In cooperative pedagogy, the student is considered as the subject of his educational activity. In this case, the teacher and the student become equal as subjects of the pedagogical process, and the process of cooperative pedagogy is formed. They will be mutual partners, friends, co-creators, co-participants, sympathizers, and co-leaders. Cooperation relations are established between teachers, administration and organizations of students and teachers, leaders, parents, and the public.

Cooperative teaching technologies are formed on the basis of cooperative pedagogy, which differs from traditional pedagogy as follows: In traditional education, the teacher is considered the subject of the pedagogical process, and the student is the object. Collaborative teaching ensures high results by developing the student's motives for education and implementing the principles of humanization of the educational process. Collaborative learning allows you to achieve the following results:

- enriches the student's learning process;
- provides students with a set of cognitive information that is distributed among them and mastered;
- arouses students' desire to learn the material;
- expands students' opportunities to form their own personal knowledge and outlook;
- increases the efficiency of two-way exchange of information;
- provides students with the necessary knowledge to prepare for independent life;

- promotes positive interactions between different cultures and socio-economic groups.

In cooperation, there is a system of dividing trainings based on hunting technology into specific types and their practical application, and below we will show some examples of these trainings:

- three-step interview;
- round talk;
- making a list;
- organization of problem solving;
- one-minute jobs;
- pair comments;
- send a problem;
- evaluation line;
- rare unit team observation;
- two-part daily quiz.

Most of these types of training involve dividing students into small groups and assigning roles and tasks to them. The following are taken into account. Cooperative teaching technologies are based on improving the pedagogic process and directing it to the student's personality. These technologies serve to create a creative environment aimed at the formation of a creative person, to increase the quality and efficiency of work [1-30]. The main processes of cooperative learning activities include: cooperative exchange of ideas, conversation, analysis, discussion, negotiation, performance of practical tasks, seeing something, making, solving problems, etc. In the organization of cooperative education classes: teacher-class, teacher-small group. Teacher-large group, teacher-student, student-student (work in pairs), small-group, group-class and other organizational forms are used. Collaborative teaching is the organization of effective cooperation by the teacher with a group of students, an individual student, and the whole class in the educational process. is a popular phrase that expresses instructional and interactive processes in the implementation of cooperation. Students work collaboratively on academic assignments in small groups and help themselves and their peers together.

In general, cooperative learning methods have the following five characteristics:

1. Students work together on a common task or learning activity, which is best learned through group work.
2. Students work together in small groups of 2-5 members.
3. Pupils adhere to socially accepted behavior criteria developed by the group in order to achieve the solution of common tasks or to carry out learning activities.
4. Pupils become positive and independent. It will be created taking into account the fact that students are required to help each other in order to find a solution to common tasks or to organize work on learning activities.
5. Pupils are personally responsible and accountable for their work, or in other words, for studying, learning.

Some non-traditional forms of lessons implemented by cooperative learning technologies:

The press conference lesson is an exercise in mastering the topic of the lesson through questions and answers.

The fun, brainy club lesson is an exercise to teach independent thinking by finding answers to interesting questions.

Working in groups is an exercise to strengthen knowledge by organizing students to perform tasks in several groups.

A mutual teaching lesson is a lesson in mastering the subject by arranging for students to explain some paragraphs of the text or similar small pieces to each other according to the content of the lesson.

A student-led lesson is an exercise to increase student activity by arranging for students to explain the topic of the lesson.

Competition lesson - organization of a pre-prepared competition of students in the class on one or more topics, and a lesson to determine the winners. Working in pairs (binary) lesson - a lesson in which students work in pairs and master the subject of the lesson together or strengthen each other's knowledge. If necessary, the pairs can be changed during the lesson.

The dialogue lesson consists of exercises to explain and strengthen the topic of the lesson by organizing dialogues with students in order to teach students to think independently and develop the skills of expressing their thoughts.

A round practice lesson consists of exercises to master a new topic or to repeat and strengthen the previous lesson based on the participation of students in turn.

Innovation lesson is a lesson to familiarize students with proposals and projects for the introduction of innovations in the field of educational science or related to school life, as well as the practical application of the results of students' creative activities. The main idea of cooperative education is not only to do educational tasks together, but also to study and learn together.

In cooperative learning technology, there are several methods of organizing cooperative learning of students:

1. Team teaching (R. Slavin).
2. Collaborative teaching in small groups (R. Slavin, 1986).
3. The "zigzag or saw" method of cooperative teaching (E. Aronson, 1978).
4. "Let's study together" method of cooperative teaching (University of Minnesota professors R. Johnson, D. Johnson, 1987).
5. The method of organizing creative research in small groups (developed by the professor of Tel Aviv University in Israel Sh. Sharan 1988).

Teaching in a team (R. Slavin) In teaching in a team, students are divided into two teams of equal number. Both teams perform the same task. The members of the team work together to complete the educational tasks and pay attention to the acquisition of the knowledge, skills and competences provided for in the subject by each student. R. Slavin said that it is not enough to give instructions to students to complete the tasks in cooperation. It is necessary to create real cooperation among students, to rejoice at the success of each student, to sincerely help each other, and to create a comfortable social and psychological environment. In this technology, when determining the quality of students' knowledge acquisition, they are compared not with each other, but with the previous results of each student. Only then, students will feel responsible and strive to learn more, mastering knowledge, skills and abilities, realizing that the results they have achieved during the lesson will benefit the team.

Collaborative teaching in small groups. In this method, small groups of 4 students are formed. The teacher first explains the topic, then organizes students' independent work. Educational assignments are divided into four parts, and each student performs a certain part of

the assignment. At the end of the task, each student thinks about the part he has completed and teaches his friends, then the group members make a general conclusion about the task. The teacher listens to the information of each small group and evaluates knowledge using test questions. Peculiar pedagogical, psychological and methodological foundations of the effective use of teaching technologies have been developed in cooperation, which are as follows: - organizational and pedagogical foundations - curriculum, program, subject of the lesson, DTS requirements and their corresponding level determination and implementation of conditions and opportunities for cooperation of training participants based on the amount of new knowledge required to be acquired; - psychological basics - taking into account the psychological and age characteristics of students, creating a comfortable psychological environment for each student in the training, organizing free communication with the quality of the lesson topic, content, used concepts, terms, definitions, formulas and ensure that other terms are understandable to readers; - methodological basis - preparation of tools necessary for training in advance, ensuring their quality at the level of requirements. Organization of communication methods and effective use of modern information technologies, etc. Factors that ensure the effectiveness of cooperative teaching: students' creative approach to the content of the lesson, analysis and criticism of information in the course of the lesson, justification of their conclusions, creative application of knowledge in new situations, allocating more time for practical tasks, cooperative learning to help each other succeed, and more.

There are 8 forms of cooperation in the science of pedagogy and psychology. They consist of the following: 1. Introduction to activity. 2. Independent actions are performed by the teacher and the student in cooperation. 3. The teacher initiates the activity and involves the student in it. 4. Imitative actions (the student who takes a lesson from the teacher acts on the basis of this example). 5. Support actions (the teacher helps the student to choose an intermediate goal and methods of achieving it, and monitors the final result). 6. Self-directed actions (the teacher participates in the assessment of the final result, indicating the common goal). 7. Self-revealing actions. 8. Self-organized actions.

CONCLUSION. The goal of cooperative learning activities is to create a control mechanism of mastery activities and joint actions, attitudes and communication. The product of cooperative activity is the emergence of new ideas put forward by students and goals related to the nature of the activity being mastered, and the desire to manage the individual's position in partnership. The method of cooperative activity should be understood as the system of joint actions of the teacher and the student. Such behavior begins with the help of the teacher to the student, the activity of the students gradually increases and turns into a practical and mental action completely controlled by them, between the teacher and the student. and the relationship will have the nature of a partnership position.

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